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The Extended Relativity Principle

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Introduction

I am neither a physicist nor a mathematician. I am just a 55-year-old man who has looked at the problem of the “theory of everything” with the eyes of a curious child. From this naïve perspective, an idea came to me so simple and trivial that it almost seemed brilliant in my own eyes.

Observation

More than four centuries ago, Galileo, by observing the passengers on a ship, realized that within a system in uniform motion, the laws of physics remain the same as in a system at rest. Centuries later, Einstein expanded that intuition to the entire cosmos, formulating special relativity and general relativity. To clarify his ideas, he often resorted to thought experiments: imaginary trains showing that time and space are not absolute but depend on the observer.

Today we can go further, no longer looking at Galileo’s ships or Einstein’s trains, but at something each of us carries within: the human body.

The cells that make up our organism, immersed in a common and cohesive environment, do not perceive external gravity as isolated particles would: they live and function according to internal rules. It is a bit like Galileo’s passengers who, inside the ship, move as if the sea did not exist, or like those traveling on a modern high-speed train: even at three hundred kilometers per hour we walk, talk, drink coffee without noticing the speed.

However, this principle holds only as long as the system remains closed to external solicitations. If a breach opened in the hull of the ship, if the train lost its doors, or if our body suffered wounds, the internal balance would be altered. In the same way, molecules in a quantum system show stable behavior as long as the environment remains isolated, but their dynamics change when the system opens and allows interactions from the outside.

This observation suggests a more general principle: what was valid for Galileo’s ships may also apply to microscopic systems, to cells, to molecules, even to black holes but it seems that a principle has been missing, one that until now appeared implicit and that with the study of quantum physics becomes necessary to state: “a principle of relativity extended” to the state of the reference system. In practice, physics is not only relative to the reference frame but also to the state of closure or openness of the system itself. I know it may sound crazy, but after these observations I would like to propose precisely a concept I will call the “Extended Relativity Principle.”

Proposal of the Principle of Extended Relativity

In its initial form, I had expressed the Principle of Extended Relativity as follows:

“The laws of physics are the same within a system only if the system is closed (coherent).”

Upon further reflection, I realized that this definition presented some inconsistencies: observable physics operates within systems that are never completely closed but exist instead in a state of partial openness with respect to their surroundings.

For this reason, I reformulated the principle in a broader and more coherent way:

“The laws of physics are the same within a system at the same level of openness or closure.”

In this new version, the validity of physical laws no longer depends on the absolute isolation of the system, but on its **relative energetic state**, expressed by its degree of openness or closure.

Systems sharing the same state of openness exhibit the same type of physical coherence, regardless of their scale or nature.

Action of Physics on Three Macro Systems

Let us suppose that the laws of physics act within three macro systems: quantum, Newtonian, and Einsteinian. Within each are subsystems that follow the same principles.

1. Quantum system

- atoms
- molecules
- crystals

2. Newtonian system

- everyday moving bodies
- fluid dynamics
- planetary systems

3. Einsteinian system

- stars and planets
- galaxies
- black holes

Taking the state changes of water as a reference, we can introduce an analogous language to describe the transitions among the three macro systems of physics:

- **Quanticization:** the transition from the Newtonian system to the quantum system.
- **Newtonization:** the transition from the Einsteinian or quantum system to the Newtonian system.
- **Einsteinization:** the transition from the Newtonian system to the Einsteinian system.
- **Quantum sublimation:** the direct passage from the Einsteinian system to the quantum system.
- **Einsteinian frost:** the direct passage from the quantum system to the Einsteinian system.

In each of these cases, the elements modify their behavior and begin to act according to the physical laws that govern the new system in which they find themselves.

Extended Relativity and Black Holes

In extreme conditions, such as inside a black hole, the transition between systems can occur so abruptly that no intermediate passage is possible. Thus arises what I define as quantum sublimation: a direct passage from the Einsteinian system to the quantum system, which passes through a moment of apparent chaos in which the laws of the two systems collide. At that moment, a new state of matter does not emerge, but rather a temporary disorder in which the particles seek a new arrangement, reorganizing themselves according to the rules of the prevailing system.

Also what I define as Einsteinian frost a direct passage from the quantum system to the Einsteinian system is theoretically possible. Some physical models suggest that, under certain conditions, a quantum system may collapse directly into a configuration governed by general relativity, without passing through an intermediate Newtonian phase. However, no direct experimental observations confirm this, although current research is attempting to explore precisely this boundary. Even in this case, the day we obtain experimental observations, we will very likely witness the same state of temporary disorder in which the laws of the two systems collide before a new balance emerges.

Theory of Black Hole Dissolution

Based on these principles, inside a black hole the prevailing system is the Einsteinian one: gravity reaches such intense values that it exerts immense pressure on matter. Not only atoms and nuclei are compressed, but even the very structure of elementary particles may give way.

According to this hypothesis, extreme pressure splits the particles, transforming them entirely into energy, in accordance with Einstein's famous relation $E = mc^2$.

In this scenario, the black hole would not collapse into a singularity of infinite density, as predicted by pure general relativity, but would undergo a genuine process of **quantum dissolution**:

- inside, particles are broken apart by extreme pressure;

- matter is converted into pure energy;
- the black hole, deprived of its constituents, progressively “empties” until it dissolves.

The final result would therefore not be a point devoid of dimensions and of infinite density, but a complete transformation of mass into energy, destined to disperse into the surrounding space.

A Bridge Toward the Theory of Everything

The atomic clock experiments that confirmed Einstein’s predictions, the experience of free fall inside an airplane that generates apparent weightlessness, and the double-slit experiment with photons showing quantum decoherence do not contradict these concepts; rather, they seem to confirm them.

The great challenge of contemporary physics is the search for a “Theory of Everything”, capable of uniting the three pillars of current knowledge: general relativity, which describes the cosmos and gravity on large scales; Newtonian physics, which governs the classical phenomena of our daily experience; quantum mechanics, which regulates the behavior of elementary particles on a microscopic scale.

These three theories work perfectly within their respective domains but present “anomalies” when pushed beyond their boundaries.

The Extended Relativity Principle offers a possible bridge: it does not claim to introduce a new force or a new law but proposes a mechanism of transition. As long as a system remains closed, its constituents behave coherently and follow the rules of the physical domain in which they are located. When instead the system opens and loses its coherence, external forces become dominant, and the constituents manifest according to the laws of the prevailing system.

From this perspective, the problem of the Theory of Everything is no longer to find a single formula valid at all times, but to understand when and how physics presents itself with a quantum face, a classical face, or a relativistic face. It is precisely the degree of openness and coherence of the system that determines which face of reality we will observe.

The Challenge

The Extended Relativity Principle presents us with an ambitious challenge: to recognize the physical characteristics of each system in order to trace its boundaries and understand its nature. Only in this way does it become possible to predict and control the transitions between different domains.

It is not a matter of replacing existing laws but of learning to read in which regime we are and how systems evolve when they open or close with respect to the outside. From this perspective, science should no longer work to find universal formulas, but rather criteria to identify the conditions under which the different manifestations of reality emerge: classical, relativistic, or quantum.

The true challenge, therefore, is to learn to navigate among these worlds without confusing them, but recognizing them as complementary aspects of a single, broader structure.

Proposal and Logic of a Z_m Index (Systemic Mutation Index)

This intuition led me to think that quantum physics, classical physics, and relativistic physics do not represent separate realities, but rather different states of openness and closure of a single universal system.

I asked myself: *how can I determine whether a system is closed or open?*

Reflecting on this question and on the precautions taken in quantum physics experiments—where systems must be completely isolated—I realized that the exchange of energy could be the key starting point.

Every system possesses its own internal energy, which ensures its coherence and stability. The openness or closure of a system depends on the amount of energy it exchanges with the external environment.

I define a **closed system** as one that has no exchange of energy with the outside. When a system begins to interact with its surroundings, it can be considered **partially or totally open**, since its internal coherence becomes partially or entirely influenced by external factors.

Starting from this concept, I define:

- **E_i** as the interaction energy or energy exchanged with the environment,
- **E_s** as the internal energy of the system.

I then introduced an **energy exchange index**, which I called Z , calculated as the ratio

$Z = E_i / E_s$, to represent the degree of energetic openness of a system: the closer Z approaches zero, the more closed the system is; the closer it approaches one, the more open it becomes and the more strongly it interacts with its environment.

Value of Z System condition Physical behavior

$Z = 0$ Closed system Quantum regime

$0 < Z < 1$ Partially open system Newtonian regime

$Z = 1$ Fully open system Einsteinian regime

A hypothetical value of $Z > 1$ would open the system toward a *metaphysical* level, whose behaviors remain unknown to science.

At this point, I asked myself what value Z would assume if, instead of the two energy terms, one used Einstein's relation $E = mc^2$.
Substituting the quantities gives:

$$Z = \frac{E_i}{E_s} = \frac{m_{ic}^2}{m_{sc}^2} = \frac{m_i}{m_s}$$

This relation shows that the index Z can also be interpreted as the ratio between the "exchanged" mass and the internal mass of the system.

In other words, Z does not describe only the exchange of energy but also represents the **degree of mutation of the system**, that is, the measure of its transition from one physical state to another: as Z increases, the system is not merely *moving* but *changing its nature*.

For this reason, I decided to call the index Z_m — **the systemic mutation index**.

$$Z_m = \frac{E_i}{E_s} = \frac{m_{ic}^2}{m_{sc}^2} = \frac{m_i}{m_s}$$

This means that:

- If $Z_m=0$: no mass or energy is exchanged → **the system remains identical to itself**.
- If $0 < Z_m < 1$: a part of itself is released, transformed, or integrated elsewhere → **mutation begins**.
- If $Z_m=1$: everything has been transformed → **the previous system no longer exists as such**.

Conceptual Extension of the Z_m Index

Since Z_m is an index constructed from the ratio between the interaction energy and the internal energy of a system, it is, in theory, possible to determine it for any stable system, regardless of its scale or nature.

To calculate it, it is first necessary to define the **system of observation**, for example, a simple container of water, a celestial body, or a biological structure and to identify the forms of energy that interact with the surrounding environment.

The interaction component E_i can be estimated, in a way conceptually analogous to thermodynamics, as the average of the incoming and outgoing energies:

$$E_i = \frac{|E_{inp}| + |E_{out}|}{2}$$

Where **E_{inp}** represents the energy received by the system and **E_{out}** the energy released to the environment.

To verify the equilibrium state of the system, I introduce an **equilibrium index**:

$$E_{eq} = |E_{inp} - E_{out}|.$$

The value of E_{eq} provides an indication of the energetic balance:

when $E_{eq} = 0$, the system is in a state of **dynamic equilibrium**.

Values different from zero indicate an asymmetry in energy exchange and therefore a variable level of openness.

In this way, **the index Z_m becomes a universally applicable parameter** for any stable system, providing a conceptual measure of its state of openness or closure.

Possible Applications of the Z_m Index

If my intuition is correct, this index could be used as a **conceptual tool** to describe the degree of energetic balance between a system and its environment.

In theory, it could prove useful in different fields of study:

- **Physics** – to represent the level of isolation or interaction of a system with its surroundings, thereby helping to understand the behavior of its internal elements.
- **Biology** – as an analogy to interpret the exchange of energy between an organism and its environment.
- **Technology and complex systems** – as a symbolic measure of a system's degree of openness to stimuli or incoming information.

In a broader sense, the **Z_m index** could serve as a **universal interpretative parameter**, capable of suggesting how the balance between internal and external energy influences the behavior of any system, from the simplest to the most complex.

Theoretical Experiment: The Water System

A first example of the application of the *Principle of Extended Relativity* can be made by considering the system of water at a pressure of one atmosphere.

This system, easily observable and reproducible, makes it possible to describe in a simple way the behavior of a body that passes through three different states of equilibrium (solid, liquid, and gaseous) as a function of the energy exchanged with the environment.

Let us assume as the **total energy of the system** E_s the amount of heat required to transform 1 kg of ice at 0 °C into steam at 100 °C, which is approximately **3008 kJ/kg**.

This value results from the sum of three main components:

- heat of fusion of ice: ≈ 334 kJ/kg;
- average specific heat of water from 0 °C to 100 °C: ≈ 418 kJ/kg;
- heat of vaporization at 100 °C: ≈ 2256 kJ/kg.

The thermodynamic values are taken from standard data (NIST – CRC Handbook – IAPWS).

Defining the **interaction energy** E_i as the amount of heat transferred or absorbed at a given instant, we can calculate the **energetic openness index** of the system as:

$$Z_m = \frac{E_i}{E_s}$$

As Z_m varies, water exhibits different forms of equilibrium:

System state	Energy supplied E_i [kJ/kg]	Z_m
Ice (0 °C)	0	0
Ice–water mixture	0 – 334	0 – 0.111
Liquid water (0–100 °C)	334 – 752	0.111 – 0.25
Water–vapor mixture	752 – 3008	0.25 – 1
Saturated steam (100 °C)	3008	1

In terms of the general principle, the water system shows that **nature does not change its laws but changes the form through which those laws manifest** as the level of energetic exchange varies.

In this sense, ice, liquid water, and vapor do not represent different realities but rather **states of the same system** observed at different values of Z_m .

Since Z_m is defined as the ratio between the exchanged energy and the total energy of the system, it is possible to **set a target value of the index** and **adjust the external parameters** (supplied power, exposure time, thermal efficiency, pressure, or insulation) to bring the system toward the chosen Z_m value, thereby driving it to the desired physical state.

For example by choosing $Z_m=0.10$ it is necessary to supply approximately **300.8 kJ/kg**: the water will be in a partial equilibrium condition in which about 90 % of the mass is liquid and 10 % still solid.

Increasing the supplied energy up to $Z_m \approx 0.25$, the system reaches the fully liquid state at 100 °C, while higher values progressively lead to the formation of vapor.

In this way, the value of Z_m becomes an **operational parameter**: by regulating the intensity of energy exchange, it is possible to *control* the observed physical state, experimentally verifying the correspondence between the level of openness of the system and the form in which the laws of physics manifest themselves.

Limits of Z_m

Since in nature there is no system whose energy exchange with the external environment is exactly zero, the value of the Z_m index never reaches absolute zero. For this reason, it is necessary to define the two fundamental limits of the theory:

$$\lim Z_m \rightarrow 0 \text{ e } \lim Z_m \rightarrow 1$$

The limit $Z_m \rightarrow 0$ represents the ideal quantum behavior, something that nature can only approximate.

All experiments that show quantum coherence, such as the double-slit experiment with photons, indicate that systems approach extremely small but never exactly zero values of Z_m . The same applies to the studies awarded the 2025 Nobel Prize, which led to the discovery of macroscopic quantum tunneling.

The limit $Z_m \rightarrow 1$ instead represents a system governed by the laws of relativistic physics. Here too, nature never reaches the exact value but only values very close to 1.

From these considerations, the limits 0 and 1 are not physically attainable values but conceptual boundaries that define the three regimes of the theory:

- **Quantum** \rightarrow when Z_m approaches 0
- **Classical / Newtonian** \rightarrow when $0 < Z_m < 1$
- **Relativistic / Einsteinian** \rightarrow when Z_m tends toward 1

Considering the values emerging from the experiments that received the 2023 Nobel Prize on strongly correlated electronic systems and the 2025 Nobel Prize on macroscopic quantum tunneling, we may tentatively place these limits at the following approximate values:

$$\lim_{\{Z_m \rightarrow 0\}} \approx 10^{-10} \text{ e } \lim_{\{Z_m \rightarrow 1\}} \approx 1 - 10^{-10}.$$

Relationship Between the Z_m Index and the Schrödinger Equation

Not being a mathematician or a physicist, I have tried to understand, at a conceptual and philosophical level, the meaning of the Schrödinger equation, which describes quantum physics.

In its standard form, $i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi = \hat{H}\Psi$ the equation indicates that a quantum system is not described by a precise position or trajectory, but by a wave function that contains all the possible states of the system and determines how this wave function evolves over time under the effect of the system's energy.

Once the fundamental concepts of the Schrödinger equation became clear, introducing the Z_m index appeared to be a natural step. Its value makes it immediately possible to understand whether a system preserves or loses its quantum characteristics. In the limit $Z_m = 0$, the equation retains exactly its original meaning, recovering the standard form of quantum mechanics.

I propose an extended form of the Schrödinger equation, incorporating the system's degree of energetic openness or closure and relating the original equation to the Z_m index as follows:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi(1 - Z_m) = \hat{H}\Psi$$

In this form, the factor $(1 - Z_m)$ acts directly on the wave function, indicating the degree of quantumness of the system.

- In the limit $Z_m \rightarrow 0$, **the standard Schrödinger equation is recovered**, and the described behavior corresponds to quantum physics.
- When $0 < Z_m < 1$, **the quantum component decreases**, indicating that the system behaves according to the laws of classical or Newtonian physics.
- In the limit $Z_m \rightarrow 1$, **quantum dynamics vanish entirely**, indicating a system governed by relativistic or Einsteinian physics.

In this way, the Z_m index allows the Schrödinger equation to be interpreted as a particular case within a more general description of physical systems.

- In the limit $Z_m \rightarrow 0$, the equation reduces to $\hat{H}\Psi = i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi$ preserving its original structure and continuing to describe quantum physics.
- When $0 < Z_m < 1$, the equation takes the form $\hat{H}\Psi < i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi(1 - Z_m)$ expressing the "distance" from the quantum regime.
- In the limit $Z_m \rightarrow 1$, the equation becomes $\hat{H}\Psi = \mathbf{0}$, indicating a relativistic system.

Conclusion

What I have tried to present is neither a complete theory nor a definitive truth, but simply an intuition, a simple idea born from looking at physics through the eyes of a curious child.

I have called it the Principle of Extended Relativity. I have defined a systemic mutation index, explored a possible application of it, and proposed a potential explanation for the fate of black holes: the Dissolution Theory.

I have imagined a new perspective from which to approach the search for a Theory of Everything, and I have outlined a preliminary mathematical approach that might translate this intuition into formal language.

I have also attempted to relate this index to the Schrödinger equation by introducing a factor that identifies the degree of quantumness, showing a perspective in which quantum mechanics appears as a special case of Extended Relativity.

As I made clear from the beginning, I am neither a mathematician nor a physicist. I do not possess the technical tools, the mathematical knowledge, and probably even the inclination to pursue calculations that are too complex. I cannot go beyond this point.

I would like to know, from people far more qualified than I am, whether this simple idea might have a plausible foundation or whether it remains only an ingenuous suggestion.

If this intuition were to prove worthy of attention, I would be glad if someone could develop it further, attempting to establish it mathematically.

For suggestions or opinions, you can contact me on Facebook:
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Thank you for your attention.

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